

A Linguistic and Literary Exploration of The Prisoners by Usman Ali as a Pastiche of Waiting for Godot

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Abstract

The present study aims to explore The Prisoners, a play by Pakistani playwright, Usman Ali, as Pastiche of Waiting for Godot. The Prisoners is a creative blend of modernist themes and style. It is deemed appropriate to make use of any of the postmodern lens to explore any postmodern text. Pastiche is a mode of intertextuality which finds vivid expression in the craft of The Prisoners. Pastiche is a style which is produced by borrowing fragments, ingredients or motifs from other works. The Prisoners, an artistic blend of modernist themes and style, written in Pakistani context, is modelled on Waiting for Godot, which has World War II in its background, therefore, the aim of this paper is to explore The Prisoners (2018) by Ali (1978) as a Pastiche of Waiting for Godot (1953) by Samuel Beckett (1906 – 1989). The paper also explores how a work of art, crafted in Eastern culture, can be a rewriting of the work of art, created in western culture. Thematically, both the plays include human predicament related to angst. Hence, human angst and predicament is a theme in Anglophone Pakistan Literature. The study reveals idealization of modern literary techniques in contemporary Anglophone Pakistani Literature.

Introduction

Analysis of *The Prisoners* a contemporary drama divulges the utility of Post-Modern literary techniques in the textual craft of the play. As Pastiche is a dominant technique in Post-Modern Literature. It develops the intertextual relationship of literary texts [*The Prisoners*] and its location in the domain of Post Modern Anglophone Pakistani literature. Pastiche differs from parody as it is not meant to mock the original style that is the function of parody rather it pays tribute and honor to the original literary piece because a text cannot occur without the original text that is imitated. This paper analyses *The Prisoners* and explores how it relates to *Waiting for Godot* with respect to its ideology and technique. As the intrinsic study of the play reveals that thematically 'existential angst' as put forward by Jaun Paul Sartre, has been used for the insight into the psychological study of the characters. Moreover, Pastiche finds much stronger expression in the style of *The Prisoners*.

As *The Prisoners* is written by Usman Ali a Pakistani born playwright. His literary competence distinguished him among the contemporary dramatists of Modern Anglophone literature. His regional consciousness replicates a hypertext of modernist themes and linguistic choices as well as the realization of his craft. His literary profile reveals his fondness of Modern theater. He has also written a script for an imaginative interview with Robert Frost in 2001. His plays written in English language include *The Prisoners*, *The Last Metaphor*, *The Breath*, *The Guilt*, *The Odyssey* and *The Flute*. He has received Taufiq Rafat Prize for drama in 2014.

The Prisoners is a play with limited characters and nearly with no action. The play is a story of five characters, four in pairs. The first pair is that of Rustum and Sohrab, both are in their thirties and are the prisoners in the play. The second pair is that of Beera and Veera who are policemen and in charge of the prison cells where the prisoners are kept. The fifth character in the play is the Master, who is in his fifties. He has a little role to play in the play. The play is divided into five panels and action circles around the five characters with offstage voices of the villagers serving as a chorus of the play. The main action of the play is about the prisoners, who are locked up in the cells of a police station in Mandibahauddin. They are the dangerous prisoners in the eyes of the villagers that have gathered outside the police station to catch them. The police are thwarting the efforts of the villagers and try to protect the prisoners so that they may not be killed extrajudicially by the villagers. The police are waiting for the aid to come but the time is short. At this point, Veera suggests Beera to surrender the prisoners to the crowd to save the life of many inside the police station but

Beera listens to his conscience and rejects the proposal. Veera wants police encounters of the prisoners but Beera blocks his plan. On this disagreement, both kill each other and the play ends.

Waiting for Godot performed in early 1953 is a play by an Irish playwright Samuel Beckett. He is an author, critic, playwright, and winner of Nobel Prize for Literature in 1969. Among many of his masterpieces *Waiting for Godot* stands out as the most prominent one. *Waiting for Godot* is a tragi-comedy and it has two Acts. It is published in French as *En attendant Godot* in the year 1952 and is produced for the first time in 1953. The play is a true success and innovation in dramatic art and in the theatre of the Absurd. There are a few characters that are engaged in conversation with each other. Vladimir and Estragon, throughout the play, wait for a mysterious character Godot that never appears on stage. During the course of the action, they encounter two more characters, Pozzo and Lucky. In an absurd manner, they discuss life and its miseries. They consider many ideas but fail to materialize any except waiting. They are a pair of human beings that do not know the meanings of their existence. They fail to understand that why they are on earth. Still, they have some hope to discover meanings in life or to find some direction to follow just to rise above their futile existence.

The play, *Waiting for Godot*, is about Existential anxiety of human beings. It has a minimum number of characters. There are only four to six characters that appear on stage and one character that is frequently referred and mentioned, remains off stage and never appears in the action of the play. These characters are in pairs. The first pair is that of tramps, Vladimir and Estragon and the second pair is that of Pozzo and Lucky. The third pair is that of the messenger boys but they appear separately in both Acts. One noteworthy thing is that there is no female character in the play. It is a tragi-comedy and has two Acts. In the first Act, Vladimir and Estragon wait for Godot. They do not have anything to do to while away their time. Therefore, they engage themselves in useless conversation and discuss several topics. During the course of their talk, they run short of words and take long pauses and silences. During the course of their talk, two more characters appear on stage. One of these is Pozzo who is a landlord. He drives his slave Lucky by means of a rope tied around his neck. Lucky carries the stuff of Pozzo as if Pozzo was on some picnic trip.

By the end of Act, I, Pozzo and Lucky leave and there appears a young messenger boy who brings a message from Godot. Vladimir inquires the boy and comes to know that Godot will not come on that day but will come the next day. After the messenger boy leaves, curtain falls.

Act, II opens at the same place; both Vladimir and Estragon see each other and try to remember the previous day's happenings. Once again, they resume their waiting for Godot and engage themselves in useless activities and talk. There is little change in the setting and of props on the stage. They discuss several topics and exhaust themselves. Again, in this Act, Pozzo and Lucky appear but this time they are changed. Pozzo is blind and Lucky is dumb. Most of the Existentialistic talk takes place in this Act. Ultimately, Pozzo and Lucky leave the stage and there appears a second messenger boy with the same message that Godot will not come on that day but the following day. The play ends on this. The play has a limited number of characters but full of dialogues.

Intertextuality

Intertextuality comes from Latin word "intertexto" which means intermix. Allen (2011) states that the term is invented in 1966 by Kristeva, who is of the view that none of the text is original as it carries the influence of other text. She believes that a text cannot be attached to a single author because the text is the product of the multiple influences on the mind of the author.

The theory of intertextuality explains that a text cannot exist as a hermetic and it further insists that no text is a self-sufficient whole; hence, it cannot function as a closed system. Some critics argue that the writer himself is a reader first. The fairest meaning of intertextuality is any allusion in one text to another. It suggests and signals some sort of interconnectedness. In other words, intertextuality involves the relation of one text to the other text. Intertextuality is a post-modern way of looking into texts with reference to the other texts.

Pastiche

The concept of Pastiche has been propounded by Fredrick Jameson. The word 'Pastiche' is derived from the Italian word 'Pasticcio' originally 'a hodgepodge of meat, vegetables eggs and a variety of other possible additions'. (Hoestery 1). Italian word has largely been replaced by the French word 'Pastiche' which (by metaphorical extension) has been used to describe art, literature, music and architecture "made up of fragments pieced together" (Dentith194)

Existential Angst

Existentialism is a philosophical theory that describes human existence. It evokes certain Existential questions such as, 'what is life, what is its meanings, how it should be lived, what is freedom, what is choice, etc.' It is true that the major Existential philosophers write with a passion and urgency rather uncommon in our own time, while the idea that philosophy cannot be practiced in the disinterested manner of objective science is indeed central to Existentialism. It is equally true that all the themes popularly associated with Existentialism—dread, boredom, alienation, the absurd, freedom, commitment, nothingness, and so on—find their philosophical significance in the context of the search for a new categorical framework, together with its governing norm.

The concept of freedom is the predicament of existence which is not developed or established against determinism. Neither it is related to the practical self-consciousness of Kant. On the contrary, it comes from the

breakdown of an activity – a direct practical activity. Freedom is neither a matter of practical activity nor that of self-consciousness rather it originates from mood that leads to anxiety (*Angst, angoisse*). *Angst* is a mental condition and linked with mood of psychology. *Angst* is the equivalent of anxiety and the experience of it. *Angst* or anxiety is a mental condition that makes the individual think about his existence in a more comprehensive way. It is closely connected with dread. It is a feeling of dread that is typically not a focused one about the condition of man and his state in this world in general.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- 1) How does pastichework in the art of characterization of *The Prisoners*?
- 2) How does the idea of angst as present in *Waiting for Godot* find expression in *The Prisoners*?

Literature Review

The relevant available research on *The Prisoners*, *Waiting for Godot*, *intertextuality* and *angst* have been searched by the researcher. Since *The Prisoners* is a new text by a Pakistani playwright, therefore, little research on it is published and available. There are a few reviews of the play and some conference papers are available

Adnan and Akhtar showcase the structure of the play and explore different techniques that the playwright uses to knot the story. It is concluded that the idea of the structure of the play is taken from one of the poems by Edward Bond titled *Have None*. In this poem, Bond expresses his heartfelt feelings about atrocities of man on man.

Further, there are reviews in the form of appreciation of the play. The first one is from Edward Bond. He appreciates the play calling it a lyrical drama in which Ali knits a strong dramatic structure. Lyricism and compact structure make a perfect drama. The drama is a combination of Ali's acute observation, complications, simplicities, human relations, compassionate understanding of man sufferings and their dignity (2018). Dr. Elizabeth of University of Essex, UK also puts high words in praise of the play. With reference to a style, she praises that Ali has a special taste for lyricism that shows itself in the play. The play is quite theatrical and full of feelings. Moreover, the dialogues are full of power and assisted by frequent non-verbal expressions (2018).

Synman calls *intertextuality* as a reflection of one text upon the other texts that triggers an uncontrollable commotion of interpretations of a text. Hence, this commotion and multiple voices of criticism of a text snatch away solid and sound single interpretation of a text. (427-49)

Yeung views *intertextuality* as a technique that enables the critic and reader to grasp a text through many other texts as the new texts are built upon the resonance of style, place, genre, time, and subject-matter. Woven into the structure of the novels, we discover an abiding concern with the formations, deconstructions, and processes of the subject. (111-27)

Sartre asserts that a lucid experience of freedom comes from anxiety (*angst*), although, it is often concealed, it still characterizes human existence firmly. For man, freedom characterizes dislocation from the consciousness or of consciousness from its subject. Therefore, there occurs a time when a subject denies his own freedom. Thus, he tries to attempt to formulate the aspects of his being as objective forces that sway him between his manners of relation with things, but this flight of freedom of the subject fails when he experiences anguish or anxiety (*angst*). (30-60)

Discussing *Waiting for Godot*, Rehman and Saeed say that *Waiting for Godot* is written in the era of World War II when people are suffering from mental depression. They state that many writers focus on the sufferings of human beings like waiting, hunger, homelessness, suicides, physical and mental illness which disturb the normal functioning of their lives and Beckett highlights the fact through the characters of his play that suffering is the essential part of human existence. Written in the background of WWII, this play deals with the human predicament on earth and raises multiple questions of Existential Philosophy. (03)

Sharma views *Waiting for Godot* with the lens of Kierkegaardian Existentialism that is Christian in nature. Therefore, he creates links between the characters and the saviour. Through God and in God man will have his salvation and all the paths that diverge from God have to come to God. The life of man, in this void, exists for some higher purpose that has to be discovered. Same it is the case with the tramps in the play that they are broken and reduced to destruction yet they do not stop looking for one, they have been seeking. (275-280)

Having examined the relevant research on *Waiting for Godot* with reference to Existentialism, it is here established that the play is by every means an Existential drama. Hence, the concept of Existentialism is a point of investigation in the play, *The Prisoners*

Methodology

The current research paper is a subjective study followed by a qualitative research approach to delineate the text of *The Prisoners* as a Post modern genre. Deconstruction of textual codes is employed to conduct a close textual analysis as a method, to collect relative excerpts from the text of the play. Therefore, textual references have been used rather than numerical data to get desired results. The plays, which serve as primary texts for this study are *The Prisoners* by Usman Ali and *Waiting for Godot* by Samuel Beckett. It also renders the comparative insight into diverging areas of dramatic composition. Hence, these texts have been

interpreted with an insight taken from Jameson's concept of Pastiche in the process of the identification of literary discourse and its alignment with modernist literary traditions in content and style. Moreover the textual interpretation is accomplished by means of *descriptive* method using the qualitative approach. Hence, angst and existential strife, has been discovered as the common theme of *The Prisoner* and *Waiting for Godot*.

Theoretical Framework

The present paper explores *The Prisoners* as a pastiche of *Waiting for Godot*. The study endeavors to establish a correlation between the plays written by two different playwrights, in subsequent divergent spatial and time frames. In this regard, the idea of pastiche, a mode of intertextuality, as given by Fredrick Jameson has been taken for insight. On thematic level of investigation and Sartre's idea of angst, propounded in *Existentialism is a Humanism* (1946), has been used for insight to interpret the text.

Pastiche is a literary technique which is used to borrow/imitate a number of elements which include characters, themes, plot, ideas from other original literary works. It is a sort of pie filling which is prepared with various ingredients. In a pastiche, the author pastes various ideas and styles together. The ideas, presented by original works' creator, are the prime source of inspiration for the pastiche.

Pastiche is like parody the imitation of a peculiar or unique style, the wearing of a stylistic mask...but it is a neutral practice of such mimicry, without parody's ulterior motive, without the satirical impulse, without laughter...pastiche is a blank parody, parody that has lost its sense of humor...(Jameson 114).

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Pastiche is a literary piece which is a wide blend of items such as themes, ideas, and characters which are borrowed from other literary works. It pertains to a rich web of connections between texts, creators and their techniques of crafting works. Since the authors are readers first, therefore, they cite, quote, and refer to previous texts in their texts. This woven web of texts can be traced and located in two works side by side.

The Prisoners is a pastiche of *Waiting for Godot* in art of characterization. As characterization is the foremost tool of dramaturgy. Interestingly, the characters in both of the selected texts under study are limited. The first pair of characters in *Waiting For Godot* is of Vladimir and Estragon. Nothing is clear about the lineage, background, nationality, race, identity of these characters. Similarly, two tramps occupy the stage in *The Prisoners*. The protagonists are Rustum and the other character Sohrab. This pair of characters seems to be directly influenced by Vladimir and Estragon. They enter the stage as the play opens and remain on the stage till the last dialogue of the play. These two do nothing except engaging in conversation inside a lockup. These flat characters resonate as if they are caricatured. As Vladimir and Estragon are symbolic of a stagnant verve and life matter in European people, who have lost their head during the two world wars in the first half of the twentieth century whereas, in *The Prisoners*, Rustum and Sohrab are the two prisoners at the police station of a regional locale. Hence the inspiration of these characters is from the *Book of Kings*(1010) by Firdawsi. A national epic of Iran, written in the Persian, it has Rustum and Sohrab as epic heroes. A writer is supposed to pick up lifelike characters but in an absurd drama characters are randomly selected and in certain cases, they are not given names. However, unlike the caricatures of Beckett, Ali's prisoners are far fewer caricatures. In real life like situation, it is more than impossible to have a pair of Rustum and Sohrab in Punjab, Pakistan. Nonetheless, they serve the purpose of the author. They do not develop over time and remain the same until the end of the play. In addition, this pair of prisoners is the protagonist of the play since there is no other surpassing and better-developed character in the play.

Second pair in *Waiting For Godot* is that of Pozzo and Lucky. These two characters undergo some physical change and there is also some change in their thoughts and ideology. In Act I, Pozzo drives Lucky by means of a long rope. Lucky serves and obeys him. They enjoy their time in the company of Vladimir and Pozzo but in Act, II, Pozzo is blind and Lucky is dumb whereas the counterpart characters in *The Prisoners* are Veera and Beera. These two characters just like Pozzo and Lucky convey the thoughts of Existentialism and to a large extent exhibit absurdity. These two characters right from the beginning till the near end of the play remain steadfast in their beliefs but ultimately yield. Hence, they meet their tragedy in each other's hands. They kill each other at the end of the play. It distinguishes TP from WFG. WFG is purely a tragicomedy, a black comedy but TP in this regard is more a tragedy and less a black comedy. Although the death of these two characters does not bring or excite any catharsis of the reader for these characters are antagonists in the play and one of these two tries to kill the protagonists (the prisoners). In this regard, the tragic end of TP does not render it a tragedy. Even then death is death and a play that involves death can rightly be labeled as a tragedy but still, there is room for an argument if TP should be called a tragedy or a black comedy. Anyway, Veera and Beera are not the exact pictures of Pozzo and Lucky in terms of their social standing and roles but as far as their actions are concerned, they are pastiche of Pozzo and Lucky. The following dialogue of Pozzo stands out the rest in the play:

POZZO: (*suddenly furious*). Have you not done tormenting me with your accursed time! It's abominable! When! When! One day, is that not enough for you, one day he went dumb, one day I went blind, one day we'll go deaf, one day we were born, one day we shall die, the same day, the same second, is that not

enough for you? (*Calmer*) They give birth astride of a grave, the light gleams an instant, then it's night once more. (*He jerks the rope*) On! (Beckett, Act, II, P. 58)

Pozzo is much frustrated now and can no longer tolerate too much questioning of the tramps. He openly manifests his state of mind that is representative of the general masses of Europe after WWI. The ultimate destiny of man is death, hence all efforts of man in this world will result in nothing. Similarly, the death of Veera and Beerai is a volume speech about the ultimate end of man. All the efforts that these two policemen make to save themselves, the police station, and the prisoners come to an end on their death. They never knew that they would leave the world one day so suddenly. Their entire efforts to sustain life become useless at the end. When they have killed each other, Rustum and Sohrab comment on them: "SOHRAB and RUSTUM: What was their last wish? RUSTUM and SOHRAB: to be buried side by side" (Ali, Panel, V, p. 129). Here the hunters themselves are hunted. Pozzo is a strong master and a landlord in Act, I but he becomes a lousy helpless blind man in Act, II. Veera and Beera who are strong and powerful and think about the false encounter of the prisoners, hire Master as a gravedigger and ready to fulfil the last wish of the prisoners are themselves fall dead by the end of the play: SOHRAB: We asked for a gravedigger. RUSTUM: And you bring MASTER? BEERA: MASTER is a gravedigger" (Ali, Panel, V, p. 129). From this, it becomes quite clear that Beckett and Ali both place the secondary characters in the same trajectory and manipulate them to serve their own purpose that is futility of life and estrangement in this material world. However, unlike Beckett, throughout the play *TP* there is scanty stage direction that confuses the reader. It suggests that the art of Ali is amateur in comparison to Beckett's. Beckett's *WFG* is finely crafted and illustrated with stage directions whereas Ali's *TP* is loose in scenes and stage directions.

Moreover, there is no character in *TP* that could be compared and contrasted with Godot of *WFG*. However, if Godot is taken as God, the savior of mankind, as a symbolic character that never appears on stage but sends his messengers that are innocent like the messenger boys of *WFG*, then there are strong references to God in *TP*. The prisoners time and again remember God the way the tramps remind each other of Godot and finally, by the end of each Act, they are given a message that Godot will not see them on that evening but the following day. V L A D I M I R: You have a message from Mr. Godot. BOY: Yes Sir. V L A D I M I R: He won't come this evening. BOY: No Sir" (Beckett, Act, II, P. 59). This message of Godot to the representatives of humanity is an indication that God Himself does not directly interfere in the affairs of man. Man has free will to set his goal and act accordingly. However, it is in the knowledge of God what man does and intends to do. Therefore, it is better for man to mend his ways instead of waiting for some otherworldly help. Where the tramps pin hopes to Godot, Rustum and Sohrab have hopes to Master. They have a desire to be buried side by side with each other and this is the only desire they have and want to be fulfilled. It is just like the desire of tramps to see Godot and receive salvation. The prisoners and the tramps both have hopes and both of the pairs lose hope as Godot does not turn up and Master cannot fulfil the last wish of the prisoners. While discussing people and Master the gravedigger, the prisoners comment. "RUSTUM: Do not they love? SOHRAB: It is merely a word for them. RUSTUM: Is it not a God's greatest gift?" (Ali, Panel, III, p. 65). This is the height of hopelessness on the part of the prisoners and it is just like the disappointment of the tramps when they receive the news that Godot wouldn't be seeing them on that particular evening after a too long tedious waiting. The main pairs of characters in both of the plays seem to be a direct illustration of each other. In other words, the characters present in *TP* have a substantial resemblance to the characters of *WFG*. One more striking similarity is that of female characters. Both of the plays do not have any female character as it does not fulfil the purpose of the writers. It suggests that the echoes of *WFG* in *TP* are vibrant and meandering. It is not only characterization of *TP* that seems to owe much to *WFG*, but the thematic aspects of *WFG* are also vivid in *TP*.

According to Sartre existence precedes essence. It is a philosophical notion that describes that man is born first and then he searches for meanings. The birth of man in this endless chaos is merely an accident and all the organizations of human life fail to sustain it permanently. There is no route to be travelled and there is no permanence to life, despite all efforts of man, it will end one day. The life in the world is short, incoherent, and haphazard and at the top of all death reduces life to nothing. In simple words, man is thrown to this limitless void without any reliable guidance issued for man. Since there are no meanings of life, man has limitless freedom. His freedom of choice is to make his life meaningful. Man is free; hence, he is responsible for his actions and choices. Existence is coupled with angst and absurdity at the face of life. It deals with individualism without any external force or guide. It is vivid that Estragon and Vladimir are trapped in their choices. They are trapped in their waiting, in the current situation they cannot act, move freely or think critically, unable to realize that they have made a choice to wait, they keep on waiting for Godot. Waiting is their choice. Several times they hit upon the idea to leave but physically they cannot move. They are trapped in an endless cycle of waiting. Certainly, it is a play in which nothing happens, there is no meaning in the life of characters, their language also fails and they make unreasonable and bizarre choices. Among all the foes 'time' is the most formidable. They want to kill it but it takes their blood and sweat. They wait for someone that never turns up. Therefore, they are

bound to suffer in the hands of time. They endure because they cannot cure it. At the end of every day, they say that another day is done. To them, each day is like the other day therefore, time loses meanings to them and has little relevance. Their memories are distorted. Every character in the play lives like a prisoner in this meaningless world. It is a prison that is made by each of the characters for him. Their inaction confines them to the prison of their circumstances. Hence, a slave that is aware of his punishment is better than the tramps that suffer without knowing his crime. Perhaps existence itself is a crime.

The prisoners and the policemen in *TP* along with the Master suffer from their circumstances. They are put into a situation like those of tamps that they cannot comprehend clearly. They are free to make choices but their insight is faulty and paralyzed. Thus, they cannot decide at the face of events what to do and what not to do. The life for the prisoners is meaningless and they have borne in their heads that their end is near. The tramps when they are utterly bored of themselves want to commit suicide unsuccessfully. Similarly, these two prisoners have yielded to circumstances and have their last wish to be buried side by side of each other. They, in the prison cell, wait for nothing although they make several choices to get rid of the situation but fail. Likewise, the policemen are also waiting for aid. They have tormented conscience and cannot decide what to do and what not to do. In the fourth panel of the play, they wait desperately for the aid to come and save them and the prisoners from the furious mob outside ready to set the police station on fire. In their dilemma of choice, Veera and Beera argue with each other either to wait for the aid or to set the prisoners free or let the villagers kill them the way they like. Tormented between these choices they entangle with each other and meet their tragic end. The Master of *TP* also suffers from an Existential crisis and is unable to know what he is doing. His job of a gravedigger is not his conscious choice and he is not satisfied with it. He wants to free himself from the burden of life but fails. The prisoners want to get rid of life but fail. The policemen do not want to die but they die. Therefore, the world of *TP* is replete with characters that suffer from an Existential crisis. Each one is with his own cross and unable to find and put meanings in his life. The world of *TP* has absurdity, loneliness, meaninglessness, waiting, suffering, and boredom that prove it as a rewriting of *WFG*.

Reading *TP* in the light of *WFG* helps a reader better understand thematic layers of *TP*. The tramps are disappointed and tired of waiting similarly the prisoners are also disappointed and tired of waiting for their final end. Estragon cheers Vladimir and Vladimir cheers Estragon at a point of utter distress. Despite all their delusions they stick to each other and complement each other. Unknowingly, they know the amount of pain and anguish of each other. Likewise, the prisoners, at a time of disappointment and sadness, stand by each other and console each other of their desired end. Although their cheerfulness is nothing but absurdity as they try to put meaning to an absurd situation, they are caught in. "RUSTUM: You are sad? /SOHRAB: No, I am not. / RUSTUM: Let me cheer you up. / SOHRAB: How?" (Ali, Panel, III, p.70).

The Prisoners are suffering from hunger, starvation, beating, pain, and the fear of approaching death. All this outer conflict emerging from the current situation aggravates the angst of the prisoners.

SOHRAB: How will we die?

RUSTUM: We cannot decide that.

SOHRAB: What can we decide?

RUSTUM: How can we live.

SOHRAB: we are approaching end...enemies outside...enemies inside. (Ali, Panel, II, p.47).

The mental state of these two prisoners also reminds the readers of the state of mind of the two tramps. Their anguish, anxiety or angst has eroded their memory and desire. They are in a world that does not make sense. These characters are in a situation that is tight, unending, and unalterable. This further aggravates their mental make-up. They cannot see clearly, plan, and decide. The amount of angst has completely overtaken all these characters in both of the texts. They are chained. To them, death is not in their hand but life is in their hand. It is quite ironic because life in no way seems to be in the hand of these characters. Although they are free to make choices and they are supposed to take responsibility of their actions yet they are chained to exercise their freedom of choice. Thus, it is bound to end in angst

The characters in *WFG* are waiting for Godot as their savior and the characters in *TP* are also waiting for agencies as their savior. Veera and Beera when they are extremely bored of this waiting for the aid and are left without options at once think about deciding the fate of prisoners. It is the height of boredom that they all of a sudden decide to get rid of it by taking extrajudicial measures of handing the prisoners over to the mob. Similar to the policemen, the prisoners are also bored to death. They have talked too much and there is nothing they can further discuss. When they are bored, they go for long silences and pauses. These silences and pauses during the course of their talk are the indications of the anguish and boredom these prisoners mentally undergo. Their situation is absolutely futile and meaningless and they cannot decide what to do and what to talk therefore, most of their talk is nothing but rubbish and useless without any purpose or reason. They want to know their

ultimate fate. They do not want to remain in an illusion as they are already too much delusional. Therefore, in their loose talk, they admire and appreciate each other for nothing and when they run out of options, they make up their minds just like the tramps to revive their conversation. "RUSTUM: What are you up to? SOHRAB: Let's play a game" (Ali, Panel II, p.47).

Here, after a long pause, Rustum opens his mouth to inquire Sohrab what to do next. It is similar to many rounds of pauses and silences followed by an absurd talk by the tramps. It is just like Vladimir's asking Estragon to say something after a round of conversation and long silence and Estragon answers that he is thinking. This is the height of angst that an individual can suffer. Similar to this is Rustum's question to Sohrab after a long round of silence that what he is thinking. Sohrab comes up with no definite answer but invites him to play some verbal game to while away the time. It is so as these two prisoners also run out of options and topics of discussion hence, they are compelled to take long pauses and silences. All this depicts the aggravated amount of angst these characters undergo. Nonetheless, their presence and talk in the worst circumstances keep each other alive to suffer more and more. It seems that if they have to suffer, they will suffer together. It is so perhaps the amount of suffering is shared and it loses its intensity. Many times, the tramps threaten each other not to see each other again but again and again, they come close to each other. Similarly, the prisoners also want to stay close to each other so that they can share each other's pain and angst.

SOHRAB: Sohrab is always with Rustum.

RUSTUM: And Rustum is always with Sohrab.

SOHRAB: Both on earth and beneath.

RUSTUM: Both on earth and beneath.

(Both embrace each other, part and sob. The longest silence of the play. Long silence)" (Ali, Panel, V, p. 122).

CONCLUSION

The discussion and analysis present that *The Prisoners* is utterly influenced by *Waiting for Godot* and Ali seems to have imported the characters and themes from *Waiting for Godot*. The number of characters in both the plays is nearly the same, there is no female character in either of the plays and there are also pairs of characters in the texts. The pair of Vladimir and Estragon is equivalent to the pair of Rustum and Sohrab. Likewise, the pair of Pozzo and Lucky is somewhat similar to Beera and Veera. Hence, with reference to characterization, *The Prisoners* seems to be a pastiche of *Waiting for Godot*.

Further, on thematic levels, it has been established in discussion and analysis that *The Prisoners* is a rewriting and rereading of *Waiting for Godot*. Both the postmodern texts have similar themes particularly Existentialism and its other tenets such as angst and absurdity. The main characters in both texts suffer from Existential crisis, angst and absurdity. They are hopeless, and engage themselves in useless talk and conversation to while away the time. Moreover, the main characters of the selected texts suffer from boredom utterly. They do not know who they really are, what they do, where have they come from, where will they go, and what will become of them? These and many more questions surround the main characters and they are unable to put meanings into their disintegrated life. In terms of themes, it seems that Ali borrows the entire plan of *The Prisoners* from *Waiting for Godot*.

Finally, it can be said that *The Prisoners* is utterly influenced by *Waiting for Godot* and Ali seems to have borrowed characters and themes from *Waiting for Godot* which makes it a pastiche play.

References

- Ali, Usman. *The Prisoners*. New Line Publishers Distributors, (2018).
- Allen, Graham. *Intertextuality*. routledge, (2011).
- Akhter, Javed. "Waiting for Godot: A disparate text." *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities* 5.2 (2015): 3-15.
- Beckett, Samuel. *Waiting for Godot: Tragicomedy in 2 acts*. Grove Press, (1954).
- Bloome, David, and Huili Hong. "Reading and intertextuality." *The encyclopedia of applied linguistics*. New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons (2013).
- Curry, Ramona. "Madonna from Marilyn to Marlene—Pastiche and/or Parody?" *Journal of Film and Video* (1990): 15-30.
- Esslin, Martin. "The absurdity of the absurd." *The Kenyon Review* 22.4 (1960): 670-673.
- Fitzsimmons, J. "Romantic and contemporary poetry: readings." Retrieved from CQ University e-courses, LITR19049. "Romantic and Contemporary Poetry (2013).
- Gadavani, Savitri. "Intertextuality as discourse strategy: The case of no-confidence debates in Thailand." *Leeds working papers in linguistics and phonetics* 9 (2002): 35-55.

- Hooti, Noorbakhsh, and Pouria Torkamaneh. "Samuel Beckett's Waiting for Godot: A Postmodernist Study." *English Language and Literature Studies* 1.1 (2011): 40.
- Khan, Abdul Bari, Hafiza Sana Mansoor, and Huma Alia. "The Impact of Absurdism in 'Waiting for Godot' by Samuel Beckett." *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education* 1.2 (2015): 312.
- Kristeva, Julia. *Desire in language: A semiotic approach to literature and art*. Columbia University Press, 1980.
- Kristeva, Julia. *The Kristeva reader*. Columbia University Press, (1986).
- Rose, Margaret A. "Pictorial Irony, Parody, and Pastiche." *Bielefeld: Aisthesis Verlag* (2011).
- Sharma, Anurag. "WAITING FOR GODOT: A Beckettian Counterfoil to Kierkegaardian Existentialism." *Samuel Beckett Today/Aujourd'hui* 2.1 (1993): 275-280.
- Sartre, Jean-Paul. "Being and Nothingness. 1943." Trans. Hazel E. Barnes. New York: Washington Square Press (1992).
- Sartre, Jean-Paul. *Existentialism is a Humanism*. Yale University Press, 2007.

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